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7 **Abstract**

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9 Walking and cycling are promoted to encourage sustainable travel behavior among children and adults. School
10 children during their travel episode to-and-from school are disproportionately exposed to air pollution due to
11 multiple reasons such as proximity to high traffic roads and peak volumes. This paper presents a route to school
12 informational intervention that was developed incorporating approaches and methods suggested in the literature
13 for effective behavioral interventions. The intervention was implemented using escorting parents/guardians
14 (N=104) of school children of Antwerp, Belgium to adopt school routes with least exposure to pollutants. Collected
15 data and its analysis revealed that 60% participants (N= 62) could benefit themselves by adopting the suggested
16 cleanest routes to school, of whom a significant proportion of participants (i.e. 34%, N= 35) have a difference of
17 average NO₂ concentration between the alternative and current route of around 10µg/m³. This information about
18 alternatives routes with their potential benefits was presented to each participant via defined study protocols.
19 Based on the feedback of participants that could potentially adopt suggested alternatives, 77% (N=48) have
20 switched their routes. These results indicated that intervention was effective, and it can bring higher benefits when
21 implemented on a wider scale.

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24 **Keywords** children; routes to and from school; traffic; exposure; informational intervention

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26 **Taxonomy** Population Exposure, Children's Environmental Health, Environmental Science

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A Route to school Informational Intervention for Air Pollution Exposure Reduction

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Abstract

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Walking and cycling are promoted to encourage sustainable travel behavior among children and adults. School children during their travel episode to-and-from school are disproportionately exposed to air pollution due to multiple reasons such as proximity to high traffic roads and peak volumes. Regular use of less polluted routes to and from school can bring significant health benefits for school children. This paper presents a route to school informational intervention that was developed incorporating approaches and methods suggested in the literature for effective behavioral interventions. The intervention was implemented using escorting parents/guardians ($N=104$) of school children of Antwerp, Belgium to adopt school routes with least exposure to pollutants. Collected data and its analysis revealed that 60% participants ($N= 62$) could benefit themselves by adopting the suggested cleanest routes to school, of whom a significant proportion of participants (i.e. 34%, $N= 35$) have a difference of average NO_2 concentration between the alternative and current route of around $10\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. This information about alternatives routes with their potential benefits was presented to each participant via defined study protocols. Based on the feedback of participants that could potentially adopt suggested alternatives, 77% ($N=48$) have switched their routes. These results indicated that intervention was effective, and it can bring higher benefits when implemented on a wider scale.

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Keywords: Children, routes to and from school, traffic, exposure, air quality, informational

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intervention,

73 **1. Introduction**

74 Good air quality is essential for the healthy living of human beings. Despite that, more than 80%
75 of the people living in urban areas of the European region are exposed to higher levels of air
76 pollutant concentrations than the World Health Organization (WHO) limits [1]. In the last decade,
77 an insignificant reduction in average pollutant concentrations has been observed in the European
78 Union (EU). In Europe, pollution and reduces life expectancy by almost 9 months [2]. It is
79 evident from the latest findings of WHO that children are most susceptible to the severe impacts
80 of air pollution [3]. Even ambient air pollution has an effect on child health before birth if the
81 mother is exposed to high levels of pollutant concentrations [4]. According to WHO statistics, 93%
82 of all the children are exposed to pollutant concentration levels above the limit values. More than
83 one in every four deaths of children under 5 years is directly or indirectly associated with
84 environmental hazards [5]. In 2016, ambient air pollution causes respiratory diseases that resulted
85 in 543,000 and 52,000 deaths in children under 5 and 5 to 15 years respectively [3].

86 In Europe, air pollution has mostly resulted from personal motorized vehicles [6]. It has found that
87 exposure to traffic-related pollutants primarily NO₂ impact on children lung development and cause
88 air passage disorders such as inflammation, chronic bronchitis, sensitization and allergies [7]. Since
89 children are growing and their immune system are still developing, so they are particularly more
90 affected by the pollutant exposure [8]. Pedrerol et al [9] has mentioned that children are highly
91 exposed to traffic-related air pollution while their home to school commuting due to high traffic
92 pollution peaks. It has highlighted in the studies that even though time spent during school
93 commuting might be less but children are exposed to a high proportion of their daily pollutant dose
94 during that episode of travel [10-12]. BREATHE project has found that children on an average
95 spent 6% of the daytime in commuting that resulted in nearly 20% of the daily integrated dose of
96 Black Carbon (BC) [12]. On the other hand, active school travel (AST) (i.e. walking and cycling

97 to school) has been encouraged and promoted worldwide using different intervention strategies
98 [13-21]. However, high respiratory rate and enhanced level of physical activity during walking and
99 cycling may result in a high inhaled dose of air pollutant. In a study for Manchester (UK) [22],
100 primary school children walking routes were simulated considering school and household
101 locations. The routes were simulated using either the shortest duration or lowest cumulative NO₂
102 or PM₁₀ concentration that a child could be exposed. The study found that for at least 50% routes,
103 walking along alternative routes which are 2 minutes longer than faster routes resulted in 5 µg/m³
104 reduction in NO₂ exposure. Routes to school that children follow must have pollution concentration
105 below the specified limits. Escorting parents, school administration, public health monitoring
106 agencies and relevant health advisors are, therefore responsible for acquainting themselves with
107 such information and then communicate accordingly. So that highly polluted routes are avoided.
108 The study for Manchester (UK) was exploratory, therefore it is required to take one step further.
109 This paper aimed at engaging escorting parents/guardians and made them aware of such
110 information to influence the selection of a better alternative route to school.

111 There are a variety of ways mentioned in the literature through which intervention can be carried
112 out by providing customized information at an individual level. For example; providing feedback
113 to individuals about their current behavior in terms of their consequences, giving justification
114 regarding possible changes in behavior using appropriate quantification of benefits it could bring,
115 taking their commitments and setting goals to bring a desired change in a particular behavior and
116 incentivize individuals to bring desired changes in the behavior [23]. These methods have tested
117 specifically about recycling and energy conservation all over the world, but there are hand full of
118 studies conducted to influence and change travel behavior [24]. In Columbia (USA), bicycle
119 proficiency program in a classroom environment was launched, and it was found that 35% of the

120 car trips were replaced with bicycle trips in a week [25]. Another study based on individualized
121 marketing strategy was conducted in Perth (Australia) in which 35000 people participated. This
122 strategy resulted in positive travel behavior change, i.e. increase of 35 %, 61 % and 9 % were noted
123 in walking, cycling and traveling as a car passenger respectively [26]. Cairns et al. mentioned that
124 improvement in public transport services coupled with efficient informational campaign resulted
125 in increased bus journeys by around 42% [27]. Similar trends have been seen for an informational
126 campaign (named as indiMARK®) to promote public transport in Germany, Australia and UK.
127 Customized information about public transportation, cycling, and walking was provided to
128 individuals that include guides to walking and cycling in the locality, schedules, and maps for
129 public transport routes, consistent with individual requirements [28].

130 Schultz [29] mentioned that for higher success and impacts interventions should be designed as
131 such that they are focused on aspects of individual travel behavior which are comparatively easier
132 to change and at the same time bring high benefits. Easy to change travel behavior can be for
133 example; the adoption of a green alternative route if the travel time difference is not significantly
134 larger from the current route, replacement of short car trips (i.e. travelling distance within 3 km) to
135 cycling when there is no time pressure and other constraints. Adopting such changes results in
136 benefits such as improve health and reduce traveling cost [30]. Efforts were made to quantify the
137 possible benefits of replacing car-based short trips by active modes and public transport. Beckx et
138 al [32] for Dutch car drivers assessed the number of short car trips that can be replaceable by active
139 modes. They found that 10% of car trips were replaceable that resulted in savings of 3% fuel
140 consumption. In another study, Fellerman found that a particular car trip, if replaced with public
141 transport, can reduce 140 g CO₂, 0.9 g carbon monoxide, 0.17 g VOC, 0.3 g NO₂ and 0.008 g PM
142 per km [33]. These traffic-related pollutants harm children health. Kim found that respiratory

143 symptoms are more elevated in children living in close proximity to traffic. Strong associations
144 were found between traffic-related pollutants and asthma and bronchitis symptoms in a highly
145 urbanized region of the United States with good regional air quality, where local air pollution is
146 dominated by vehicular sources [34]. As children are especially more sensitive to the adverse
147 effects of air traffic-related air pollutants, therefore home to school routes with lower pollution
148 levels could provide higher health benefits for them.

149 Informational interventions designed and implemented so far are based on strategies to educate,
150 motivate and encourage individuals by providing general information to promote pro-
151 environmental travel behavior. There is no such structured and organized effort found in which
152 information is provided considering the context of an individual with a detailed illustration of the
153 consequences of such behavior and benefits of suggested changes in behavior. For example,
154 strategies are not based on examining their details of travel behavior, so that focus should be on
155 improving a specific part of their travel behavior. Such as providing individual specific guidance
156 about safer and lesser pollutant routes to school with the benefits of suggested changes. It is
157 important that in the intervention programs, this aspect is highlighted more clearly so that
158 children/escorting parents are more inclined to follow such routes which are potentially safer in
159 relation to pollutant exposure.

160 The objective of this study was to find out the replaceable potential by examining children's current
161 route to school pollutant exposure and availability of lesser polluted routes. Furthermore,
162 exploitation of that replaceable potential by setting up an informational intervention and assess that
163 up to what extent such intervention is effective. The intervention has been set up primarily by
164 providing customized information about the consequence of current and suggested school travel
165 choices concerning the following aspects.

- 166 • Exposure to air pollution based on current school travel choices
- 167 • Details such as distance, travel time etc. about available walking/cycling school routes
- 168 • Exposure to air pollutant based on suggested walking/cycling school routes
- 169 • Benefits of proposed route changes

170 The details regarding the design, implementation and effectiveness of this informational
171 intervention are well explained in the following sections. This paper is structured as follows:
172 Section 2 explains the data collection techniques adopted for gathering required data sets along
173 with data integration and processing to get the desired information. Section 3 presents details of
174 the implementation of the designed intervention. Section 4 discusses the obtained results of the
175 study. Section 5 provided a discussion on the results along with practical implications followed by
176 the conclusion section.

177 178 **2. Materials and methods**

179 This section provides details about the required data sets along with their acquisitions methods.
180 Based on these acquired data sets, a distinct mechanism was developed to generate easy to adopt
181 school travel choices keeping in view the air quality. The generated output was used to set up
182 information based behavioral intervention to influence changes in the route to school. Further
183 insights about each of the steps involved are mentioned below.

184 *2.1. Data Required and acquisition methods*

185 A range of dataset was acquired to detect current and alternative home to school routes along with
186 their pollutant exposure level. These data sets comprised of not only detailed information taken
187 from the escorting parents or children regarding home to school routes but also about the pollutant
188 concentrations in that microenvironment. Furthermore, additional information such as availability

189 of walking and cycling routes along with other associated features were also acquired and stored
190 as third party dataset. The paragraphs below provide details about how these datasets are acquired.
191 Children school route information was recorded using Route2School online platform developed in
192 house by Transportation Research Institute (IMOB) at Hasselt University. This online platform can
193 be accessible both using mobile (<https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.dhcollator.routetoschool>)
194 and web application (www.route2school/login). This user-friendly online platform
195 shown in Figure 1 was provided to the escorting parents/guardians, where they can easily record
196 their children's home to school information. Parents/guardian fed in some initial information such
197 as home and school address along with the usual travel mode. Based on this, an appropriate route
198 was displayed on the GUI of OpenStreetMap. Parents/guardians could adjust the route by dragging
199 it on the currently used route if required, so that recorded route have the right combination of road
200 links.

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Figure 1: Route2School mobile application (left) and web application (Right) user interface

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205 Children are highly exposed to on-street traffic pollutants while commuting along busy roads [35].

206 In the Flanders region of Belgium, about 50 % of the total NO₂ emission is caused by road traffic.

207 As such, NO₂ is an important marker for quantifying traffic-related air pollution [36]. According

208 to WHO, children are more vulnerable to the impacts of NO₂ compared to other pollutants [3].
209 NO₂ concentration data at fine spatial resolution is required to get insights into child exposure
210 while school commuting. So in this regard, hourly annual NO₂ concentration at a spatial resolution
211 of 10 m by 10 m grid map is obtained for Flanders from Flemish Institute of Technological
212 Research (VITO). This map is depicted in Figure 2. It is based on the measurements recorded from
213 various stations in Flanders and the surrounding regions, using interpolation and high-resolution
214 modeling. Different concentration levels of NO₂ are shown using green, light green, yellow, red
215 and purple colors from the lowest to highest concentration levels respectively. ATMO-Street (RIO-
216 IFDM-OSPM) model is used in the estimation of hourly NO₂ concentration values at street level.
217 This holistic model is based on the integration of the following models [37].

- 218 • RIO is a land use regression model for the interpolation of hourly pollutant concentrations
219 as measured by the monitoring stations
- 220 • The IFDM (Immission Frequency Distribution Model) is a bi-Gaussian plume model used
221 for calculation of the air quality based on meteorological data and the emission of air
222 pollutants
- 223 • OSPM model contains detail information about the street configuration and incorporates
224 the impact of street canyon effect while simulating street-level concentrations.

225 The advantage of the RIO-IFDM-OSPM combination is that the air quality can be estimated
226 with a high spatial resolution down to street level. The validation analysis was performed at
227 various stages in the model chain, explaining the strength of different components for the
228 development of concentration maps. The model represents the spatial variability at urban to
229 street level scale with an R² value of 0.86 [38]. A recent study conducted in Milan, Italy
230 predicted cleanest (having less black carbon exposure) home to school routes using the LUR

231 model [39]. For 2 months, children BC exposure on home to school routes were also measured
232 using personal monitoring kits. The exposure estimated using kits and LUR model showed
233 good agreement having Pearson's $r = 0.74$, Lin's Concordance Correlation Coefficient = 0.6.
234 The results indicated that the prediction of cleanest school routes can be done using LUR
235 estimates.

236 Figure 2: Map showing 9th hour (08:00 am) average annual NO₂ concentrations of Flanders for school days

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239 Data about infrastructure related to cycling and walking is also required in computing alternative
240 routes based on active commuting. This information was obtained from available route planner
241 platforms such as Graph Hopper Directions API in which routes are optimized with the help of
242 OpenStreetMaps. Details associated with each route such as gradient, number of intersections,
243 availability of segregated path etc. could also be found using this API [40].

244 2.2. Rules-alternatives active school routes

245 Rules to detect alternative walking/cycling routes to school are based on the threshold limits and
246 constraints involved in children school commuting. These threshold limits and constraints were
247 identified from the contextual information and past studies done in this regard. In one such study

248 threshold distance of 3 km from home to school is suggested to promote active school travel in
249 Flanders [41]. The rules to identify the most feasible route alternatives are as follows:

- 250 • Alternative cycling routes must be ≤ 3 km if the current route is ≤ 2.5 km
- 251 • Alternative walking routes must be ≤ 1.25 km if the current route is ≤ 1 km
- 252 • The difference of alternative to current route must be ≤ 0.25 km if the current route is ≤ 3
253 km.
- 254 • The difference of alternative to current route must be ≤ 0.5 km if the current route is ≥ 3
255 km.
- 256 • In case of walking, footpaths are available all along the route
- 257 • In case of cycling, segregated bike lanes are available at least halfway along the route
- 258 • Crossings in the bike route/footpath are limited to 3
- 259 • Route average gradient is not more than 10%

260 *2.3. Data Processing*

261 The mechanism adopted to detect less polluted walking/cycling routes to school involves various
262 processes and computations. It starts with retrieving recorded home to school routes from R2S
263 platform followed by identifying feasible walking/cycling alternative routes and ends by evaluating
264 pollutant exposure involved per trip. Further, the information generated was organized and
265 structured in a way that it is easily incorporated in the intervention tool. The details about how
266 various data sets integrate during different processes and how they flow from one process to
267 another are explained below and depicted in Figure 3.

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Figure 3: Flow Diagram for the assessment of less air polluted alternative school routes

Initially, all recorded routes were retrieved from R2S platform and stored in the database as a single file in .dbf format. Each route has certain attributes such as project id, route id, home and school location and mode used. The home and school location are used as one of the inputs to detect alternative walking/cycling routes. For this purpose, an existing algorithm could be used such as k-shortest path approach, link elimination and simulation methods [42]. Depending upon the simple input data requirement, the k-shortest path approach was selected. In the 1st phase, the process was initiated by executing k-shortest path algorithm that requires cycling /walking network data (obtained from ordinary street maps for Flanders region of Belgium) and origin-destination details (x,y pairs) as input. The resulting output was stored as “Alternatives Routes”. The detected route

331 weighted average formula based on the total number of data points for each route. For each
332 individual, alternative routes were further compared and ranked from lower to higher average
333 concentration values for the development of intervention information package.

334 *2.4. Intervention tool: Customized Information Package*

335 Mobility based informational interventions have a pull effect and ability to effect socio-cognitive
336 aspects of individual travel behavior by applying strategies based on information dissemination
337 and persuasion [43]. Therefore the efficacy of such an intervention primarily depends on the ways
338 how the information is designed. In past studies, various methods were adopted and examined for
339 their effectiveness [24]. Based on the review by Adnan et al [44] it was found that an informational
340 interventions based on the following approaches were more appropriate to influence change in
341 travel behavior. A brief explanation of these approaches are as follows:

- 342 • *Feedback*: monitoring individuals, and then providing feedback regarding their travel behavior
343 such as how much is their exposure to air pollutant for their activity-travel routine.
- 344 • *Justification*: Reasons can be provided about the recommendation of a particular change in
345 behavior such as if short trips are made via active travel modes then what are their benefits.
- 346 • *Instructions*: Procedural information is provided to carry out specific behavior; such as avoid
347 car use in short trips within 3-5 km.

348 Keeping in view the above approaches, an online customized information package was designed
349 that act as an intervention tool to influence the change in school travel behavior. The overall
350 effectiveness of the customized information package also significantly depends on the structuring
351 i.e. organization and presentation of the information. So each section of the Customized
352 information package is organized as follows:

- 353 • *Contextual information* with infographics to increase the awareness related to air quality and
 - 354 pollutant exposure impacts, which are easy to understand and digest.
 - 355 • *Customized Feedback* regarding a quantitative measure of current and alternative school travel
 - 356 choices with the description of their impacts in terms of pollutant exposure.
 - 357 • *Description of the personal benefits* achieved in terms of reduction in pollutant exposure level
 - 358 by adopting an alternative route and long term health impacts.
 - 359 • *General suggestions and tips* on how to avoid pollutant exposure in an urban environment.
- 360 Further to avoid any confusion, the routes of the detected alternatives were marked on the GUI of
- 361 google street maps and embedded in the Customized Information Package as shown in Figure 5
- 362 below.

363 Figure 5: View of embedded routes in online Customized Information Package

364 3. Intervention Study Details

365 3.1 Study Area context

366 The study area consists of Berchem and Borgerhout region of Antwerp city as shown in Figure 6.

367 The city has a central location in a highly urbanized region in Europe. Since it is an important port

368 city and transportation hub, the commuter and the international transit traffic are also part of the

369 traffic flows in and around the city [45]. The Antwerp ring road carries most of the traffic in this

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371 region. On average 300,000 vehicles use this road link daily in which 27 % are freight vehicles.
372 The Antwerp ring road is passing through areas such as Borgerhout with population densities above
373 11,000 inhabitants/km². Around 352,000 people reside within 1.5 km radius from the ring road
374 [46]. 12 schools and 75 nurseries are located in the nearby area, where daily average particulate
375 concentrations were observed above EU threshold limits. As a result, it is a recognized polluted
376 hotspot, particularly NO₂, which has adverse respiratory effects, especially in children [47]. This
377 background information is a major motivation factor to carry out this study.

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379 Figure 6: Figure showing localities along Ring road within study area

380 *3.2 Recruitment Process*

381 Before the launch of a campaign for the participant recruitment, ethical approval was taken from
382 the Social-Societal Ethics Committee (SSEC) of Hasselt University. Information about the study
383 was floated using social and local media. It was mentioned that the study target group should belong
384 to the surrounding areas of the Antwerp ring road, who are interested to know less polluted school
385 routes for their kids. 113 interested citizens, i.e. parents of elementary school kids, contacted us via
386 email in the month of February 2019. They were asked to join the study by signing an electronic
387 informed consent form. There were some dropouts as well, and 104 participants managed to

388 complete the study successfully. It was observed that 85% of the parents escorted their kids to and
389 from schools. The overall methodology of the study was designed in such a way that it can be
390 managed remotely, without the requirement of physical contact. Therefore, citizens who are
391 participating in the study needed to have sufficient knowledge of e-mail based communication and
392 some know-how of web-based tools.

393 *3.3 Implementation Procedure*

394 Implementation of the study was done in four stages. At the start of the study, participants were
395 asked to fill in the online introductory questionnaire by sending them an online link via email. This
396 task aimed to know about the individual (escorting person/guardian) socio-demographic details
397 and their awareness about air pollution. In the 2nd stage, participant current school travel behavior
398 was recorded. The detailed information about how to access and work with Route2school online
399 platform was sent via email. Escorting person/guardian marked home to school route with required
400 attributes and sent the information to the database. More than one route was recorded if different
401 routes were followed at the start and pack up time or different days of the week. Recorded
402 information about current school behavior is processed and analyzed, as mentioned in section 2.2.
403 Participants were given feedback in the form of online Customized Information Package. This
404 package provided insights about actual and suggested school travel choices along with their
405 consequences. The layout of the electronic version of this package is shown in figure 7. After the
406 week, participants were asked to fill in the feedback questionnaire to know about the possible effect
407 of information provided and generic comments about the study. The whole procedure is well
408 depicted in Figure 8.

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Figure 7: Layout of the Information Package (Dutch version)

Figure 8: Procedure involved in the implementation of the study

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418 **4. Results**

419 This section highlights the main findings of the study implemented in the Antwerp region. Analysis
420 of different data sets collected during the study is presented in detail. Along with the descriptive
421 and qualitative analysis of the contextual data, current and suggested school travel choice were also

422 estimated that provide key results on which information intervention study was based. Furthermore,
423 effectiveness of the air quality based information intervention is also presented.

424 *4.1 Descriptive analysis*

425 This section highlights key socio-demographic characteristics and views of the study participants
426 about school commuting and air pollution. Furthermore, some situational factors such as walking
427 and cycling infrastructure details were also gathered. Table 1 below illustrates the distribution of
428 socio-demographic characteristics of the participants involved in this study.

429 Table 1 provides interesting details, it can be noted that the majority of the participants in terms of
430 the 2 age groups, i.e. between 30–50 years old have participated in the study. Female participation
431 is at the higher side compared to males. Majority of participants have education status equivalent
432 to bachelor's degree or above (i.e.79 %), and income distribution is similar to a typical negatively
433 skewed with a median value around 35,000 € per annum. According to Eurostat [58], monthly
434 minimum salary of a Belgian resident for year 2019 is 1593.81 euros which is around 19,000 euros
435 per annum. That is the reason that there is a least probability that participants fall in the income
436 category less than 10,000 euro per annum. Keeping in view the sociodemographic of the Belgians,
437 the sample included participants from all classes. It can also be observed from Table 1 that most of
438 the families have a size not more than 4 members and the age of the kids who are escorted to school
439 are nearly uniformity distributed among three age categories. Further, around 97 % of citizens have
440 ownership of a car in which 33 % possess 2 cars, but at the same time, it is also found that all study
441 participants have bicycle ownership as well.

442 Indicators of environmental awareness were also gathered. Based on the distribution of participant
443 responses, it can be concluded that majority of the respondents have an understanding of the
444 environmental issues and they agreed that humans should take responsibility to improve the

445 environmental condition. It is noted that around 61% of the citizens have the opinion that
 446 environmental pollution is a problem in their locality. Respondents are also well aware of the
 447 significance of physical activity for children by showing 85 % agreement to such a statement.
 448 Regarding the active mobility infrastructure, participants showed mixed views about the facilities
 449 available to adopt active travel options such as bicycle and pedestrian facilities. 79 % of the citizens
 450 have the view that car use should be more restricted by taking some hard policy measures. It depicts
 451 the situation that there is more room to improve the facilities that encourage healthy and active
 452 travel behavior among individuals in the study area.

453 Table 1: Socio-Demographic characteristics distribution of study Participants
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Characteristics	Statistics with description
Gender (escorting parents/guardians)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Male 34 % • Female 66 %
Age escorting parent / guardian	No of escorting parents expressed in %age with respect to age group is summarized as follows: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • B/W 30 - 40 years 39.5 % • B/W 41 - 50 years 51.5 % • B/W 51 - 60 years 3.0 % • Above 60 years 6.0 %
Employment status	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Full time work 54.6 % • Part time work 21.2 % • Self-employed/business 12.1 % • Retired 6.0 % • Others 6.1 %
Qualification level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bachelor diploma 15.2 % • Master's degree 45.5 % • Professional degree 15.2 % • Doctorate Degree 3.0 % • High school graduate, diploma or the equivalent 15.2 % • Trade/technical/vocational training 6.1 %

Household income	Participants are categorized in %age w.r.t total household income per annum as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 10,000 to 24,999 € 12.0 % • 25,000 to 49,999 € 33.2 % • 50,000 to 74,999 € 27.3 % • 75,000 to 99,999 € 15.2 % • 1,00,000 to 1,49,999 € 9.1 % • 1,49,000 to 1,99,999 € 3.2 %
Total family members	Participants are grouped with respect to family size (expressed in numbers) as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 02 members 12.12 % • 03 members 33.33 % • 04 members 33.33 % • 05 members 18.18 % • 06 members 3.03 %
Age of kids	No of kids expressed in %age with respect to age group are as follows: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3-5 years 30.4 % • 6-8 years 33.3 % • 9-12 years 36.3 %

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457 *4.2 Travel Routes and their Exposure levels*

458 Children’s school travel behavior was recorded using Route2school online platform. Figure 6 is

459 showing localities of Berchem and Borgerhout along the ring road within the study area. As these

460 localities are in close proximity to the ring road, so residents are highly influenced by the traffic-

461 related pollutants, specifically the weaker group such as children. To reduce this impact easy to

462 adopt alternative walking/cycling route choices with least exposure are identified for influencing

463 the travel behavior of escorting parents/guardians and children.

464 The route detection algorithm is used to identify possible cycling and walking route alternatives

465 with related attributes such as travel time and distance. Subsequently, the current and alternatives

466 routes were processed further to get exposure per route, as discussed in section 2.2. The exposure

467 associated with current and most suitable alternative (having the least exposure) routes, for a study

468 group, is presented in figure 9 as a box plot. This way of graphical illustration is used to compare

469 the exposure distribution for current and alternative routes for study participants. Based on the
470 comparison of box plots, it can be seen that the overall distribution pattern looks similar as both
471 have almost the same range. However, there are noticeable differences in quartile and median
472 values as alternative routes have lower values. The comparison between the 2 box plots suggests
473 that the alternative routes have the potential to reduce NO₂ exposure on children while school
474 commuting.

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Figure 9: Box plots representing current and alternative route exposure

478 In order to better communicate escorting parents/guardians about the exposure to different
479 levels of NO₂ concentrations, we adopted a categorization based on the limiting values set by
480 WHO and European Environmental Agency (EEA) [3,48]. Three categories are defined, i.e.
481 Low, moderate and high, to characterize the exposure of current and alternative routes. If the
482 average concentration value is less than or equal to 40 ug/m³, the route is categorized as having
483 low exposure, moderate if values are 41 – 50 ug/m³ and high if values are greater than 50 ug/m³.
484 Figure 10 is showing an overview of the exposure variation in the participant current routes. It
485 is found that almost one-third of the routes fall in each category. Around 67% of the participants

486 follow the routes that have exposure values in moderate and high categories, which depicts that
487 every 2 out of 3 children are exposed to concentration values above the threshold limits. The
488 situation demands actions from the authorities. However, in the short term, the exposure could
489 be reduced by encouraging escorting parents/guardian to adopt pro-environmental route
490 choices.

491 Figure 10: Graph showing actual route distribution based on exposure categories
492

493 It is also important to know whether there is any positive difference between exposure of current
494 and alternative route for a child and escorting parent? For alternative routes, exposure categories
495 are assigned similarly and compared to know about the possible benefits in relation to exposure if
496 escorting parents/guardian may choose an alternative route. The results of this comparison are
497 presented in Table 2. The number in each cell in table 2 is representing the %age of the participants
498 whose exposure category can possibly be changed, such as moderate to low, high to low etc. About
499 17 % of the participant's exposure category changed from moderate (current route) to low
500 (alternative route). Similarly, for 7 and 10 % participant's exposure category can be shifted from
501 high to low and high to moderate category. Therefore, it can be concluded that the significant
502 proportion, i.e. 34 % of the participants has alternative routes with better air quality as compared

503 to their current choice of route. This potential route shift can significantly help to avoid health risks
504 associated with high NO₂ concentrations.

505 Table 2: Participant's exposure category change from current to alternative routes

% Participant's exposure category shift from actual to alternative routes			
Alternative Routes	Current Routes		
	Low	Moderate	High
Low	30	17	7
Moderate	3	20	10
High	0	0	13
Grand Total	33	37	30

506
507 Furthermore, the numbers in Table 2 also depict no change in pollutant exposure category for one-
508 third participants (i.e. the numbers 20 and 13 in the table). We also found out the exact differences
509 in exposure values between the current and alternative routes within each category, to see if there
510 are still some benefits exist if participant adopts alternatives routes (though their exposure category
511 remains same after shifting). It is found that there are some significant differences, i.e. reduction
512 in concentration values of alternative routes, as compared to current routes in each category (See
513 Figure 11). The average reduction for Low category is found to be 1.11 µg/m³ with minimum and
514 maximum values of -1 and 5, respectively. A negative value of -1 is showing that some participants
515 don't have any better route as compared to their current route. The mean value of concentration
516 difference between current and alternative routes is 0.75 µg/m³ (-4 to 6) for a participant lie in the
517 moderate category. Similarly, the mean positive difference of 6.25 µg/m³ is recorded for the
518 participants fall in the High category with extreme values of -3 to 10. It can be seen that the average
519 difference for High category is more as compared to low and moderate. The higher the reduction
520 in pollutant concentration values while commuting there is less health risk involved. This link has
521 been statistically established by researchers in various epidemiologic studies [49-51] .

Figure 11: Box plots demonstrating exposure difference distribution with in the same category

522
 523
 524 In one of the WHO projects, i.e. HRAPIE (Health risks of air pollution in Europe), health impacts
 525 of air pollution were assessed. It was quantified that there is a relatively increased risk ($RR^1 =$
 526 1.021) of bronchitis symptoms in children aged 5–14 years per $1 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ change in annual mean
 527 NO_2 concentration [51]. In another study, stronger associations between highway proximity and
 528 particles on the exhaled nitrogen oxide in children with asthma, showing increased inflammation
 529 of airway [49]. Based on these findings, we can say that adopting alternative routes that lie in the
 530 same exposure category i.e. but with some reduced exposure to NO_2 concentration can also bring
 531 health benefits for further 26 % of participants i.e. school children.

532 In most of the past studies, RR (relative risk) is estimated based on $10 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ increase of NO_2
 533 [51,49,50,52,53]. On similar lines, an effort was made to quantify health impacts due to long term
 534 exposure of NO_2 in HRAPIE project. It was found that increases in NO_2 concentrations (per 10
 535 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, annual means) are associated with increases in all-cause mortality with RR of 1.055 (95%
 536 CI: 1.031–1.080) [51]. A recent meta-analysis of 48 cohort studies conducted by Atkinson et al

¹ Relative risk is a ratio between the chance of occurrence of an event in the exposed group as compared to the non-exposed group. RR gives information about the higher and lower likelihood of an event between the exposure and the non-exposure group.

537 came up with the conclusion that there is a positive association between long term concentrations
538 of NO₂ and all-cause mortality (RR=1.02 [95% CI: 1.01-1.03] per 10 µg/m³ increment in NO₂).
539 Similar association was found for cause-specific such as cardiovascular (RR = 1.03 [95% CI: 1.02,
540 1.05]), respiratory (RR=1.03 [95% CI: 1.01, 1.05]), and lung cancer mortality (RR=1.05 [95% CI:
541 1.02-1.08]) [54]. As mentioned earlier that in our study every 1 out of 3 participants (kids with
542 escorting parent) have alternative routes available with reduced NO₂ annual concentrations of
543 around 10 µg/m³. So we can say that these kids and escorting parent can reduce the risks associated
544 with exposure to high NO₂ concentrations by adopting the alternative routes. In total around 60 %
545 (34% + 26%) of the participants (N= 62) have alternative routes available with reduced levels of
546 NO₂ concentrations as compared to current routes.

547 *4.3 Intervention Effectiveness*

548 In this section, some insights into the effectiveness of the implemented intervention are provided.
549 The effectiveness is measured based on the responses of the questionnaire filled by the participants
550 after the intervention. The feedback questionnaire asked the participants the following questions.

- 551 1. Did you learn something new by participating in this study? If you select YES, then please
552 explain why?
- 553 2. Having learned about your exposure to air pollution, do you think you will change the way
554 you escort your kid to school? Yes/No please explain
- 555 3. Do you think there is something you can do to reduce air pollution in your city? If you
556 select YES, then please explain why?
- 557 4. Did you like the study? Rate from 1(hate) – 5 (love)

558 Around 88 % of the participants mentioned *YES* as the response to the 1st Question. The responses
559 are encouraging as most of them reported that participation in the study increases their knowledge

560 related to pollutant exposure and further about the commuting to school in a healthier way. From
561 the 60% participants (N=62) that could bring some benefits by adopting alternative routes, 77 %
562 of the participants (i.e. n=48) responded positively to the 2nd Question by reporting that they
563 started following the suggested alternative routes to school with the least exposure to air pollutants.
564 We further analyzed the reasoning for those 23 % participants who responded negatively to this
565 question. 13% of them are those who also did not show agreement with the question asked about
566 “environmental pollution in a locality is a concern” in their response to the introductory
567 questionnaire. This means that there is a need for awareness campaigns to educate people about
568 health impacts due to pollutant exposure. Another 10% participants were those who showed
569 reluctance to follow the suggested alternative routes due to safety concerns. It is observed that the
570 children of these participants are mostly from the age category of 9 -12 years old. This concern is
571 probably because children started going to school independently at this age and parents are extra
572 conscious about their safety. Some of the responses are provided as it is.

573 “the alternative route is certainly greener but perhaps not safer for
574 young cyclists due to lack of separate cycle path and footpath”.

575 “Because the alternative route is even more dangerous than the
576 current one - first safety, then air pollution”.

577 For question 3, 40 % of the participants showed good civic sense by responding positively that
578 they can take certain actions to reduce air pollution in the city. A couple of respondents showed a
579 commitment to increase cycle use and reduce car use as much as possible. Some participants have
580 an intention to plant trees in their locality. One of the participants has a plan to encourage
581 municipality about the improvement in walking/cycling paths. The escorting parents from age
582 group below 40 years seem more enthusiastic and pro-environmental as most of them fall in the

583 age category of 30 – 40 years, as mentioned in Table 1. Participants in overall like the study by
584 giving a positive rating, the average score (from 104 participants) estimated is around 4.1 out of 5.

585 **5. Discussion**

586 In the last two decades, many environmental and transportation experts have explored the effect of
587 traffic-related air pollution on active commuting. However, very few have tried to find the
588 measures that commuters can proactively use to protect themselves from high pollutant exposure
589 and its impact. This study examines alternative routes for active school commuting as one such
590 measure and evaluates its potential. Based on the rules for selection of alternatives routes, as
591 mentioned in section 2.2, 60 % of the participants have the availability of alternatives routes in
592 which significant reduction of NO₂ exposure has been observed. This finding is consistent with
593 those reported in other limited studies conducted to optimize routes for exposure reduction. A study
594 for Greater Manchester, UK, was conducted in which the fastest home to school routes and routes
595 with least NO₂ exposure were simulated. For nearly 60% of the walking routes, a less polluted
596 route was found, based on cumulative NO₂ exposure [22]. A study was conducted in Montreal,
597 Canada with the aim to calculate the shortest route (based on length) and the “cleanest route” based
598 on NO₂ exposure. The Montreal study has found alternative routes for 57% of the cycling trips
599 with a mean decrease in NO₂ concentration of 1.45 µg/m³ [55]. The results of these studies are
600 comparable to our study and it can be concluded that there is a significant potential to reduce school
601 commuting exposure by suggesting alternative routes. In our study, we not only estimate this
602 potential but also designed and implemented an informational intervention for its exploitation.

603 Several school travel behavior change initiatives have been taken to improve physical activity
604 among children. These initiatives also reduce traffic congestion and pollution by discouraging car
605 use. “Safe Route to School” (SRTS), “Walking School Bus”, “Ride2School Program”, “School

606 Travel Planning” (STP), “Bikeability” and “Beat the street” are among one of the prominent
607 implemented programs targeted to promote physical activity in America (US), Australia, New
608 Zealand, Canada and United Kingdom (UK) [56]. US government has spent around 1 billion dollars
609 in the SRTS program to promote AST and the result was 4.5 % absolute increase in walking and
610 cycling over the course of 5 years [57]. Ride2School initiative was taken in Australia with
611 insignificant improvement in active school commuting of 2 % [15]. Similarly, STP was conducted
612 in New Zealand and Canada with a modest increase of 2.1% and 1.7 % respectively in active
613 school travel observed from the student reported follow-up data [13,16]. In UK a technology-based
614 intervention “Beat the street” has implemented in school that resulted in 10 % increase in the AST
615 in the intervention group[14]. The interventions mentioned above tried to influence children’s
616 school travel behavior by focusing on strategies like education, motivation, encouragement, and
617 infrastructure improvement. All of these intervention provided the generic information without
618 focusing the individual contextual information. It is found that intervention targeting an easy travel
619 behavioral change are more effective provided that they are equipped with individual-specific
620 feedback and benefits of change. Indimark® is found to be one of the successfully initiative
621 implemented in Europe and Australia by providing tailored feedback to promote individual pro-
622 environmental travel behavior. The reported estimate of travel behavior change is a maximum of
623 15 % which shows its impact [28]. Keeping in mind the similar past studies, we designed the
624 intervention by combining multiple strategies such as education, encouragement, feedback
625 (customized) and justification (benefits/relevance) to convince participants to adopt suggested
626 school routes for pollutant exposure reduction. It is observed that the implemented intervention has
627 a significant effect on participant school travel behavior. The reason behind such a positive impact
628 is due to the high level of associated benefit. Furthermore, other reasons for its significant effect
629 are the relevance of the intervention to the study area (pollution is a concern for the residents of

630 the region) and targeting vulnerable group (i.e. parents/guardians are sensitive to their children
631 health).

632 In addition to the above, the results of the interventions effectiveness results provide evidence that
633 such study can be successfully managed remotely without any face to face connect by using apps
634 (e.g. R2S online platform) and web tools. However, it is should be decided carefully based on the
635 target audience. The concept and framework of this interventional study can be applied together
636 with other studies in several ways. For example, in the short term, it can be used to assist the
637 Route2school program in Belgium to select walking and cycling routes that address both safety
638 and air quality concerns for children while school commuting. In the long term, this initiative can
639 be coupled with other interventions set by cities to promote green and active commuting to improve
640 accessibility, safety, and air quality for travelers in a holistic manner.

641 **6. Conclusions**

642 This paper describes the development, application and analysis of the air quality based
643 informational intervention to promote healthy (less polluted routes) school commuting. The
644 customized information is provided to each individual about the active school travel choices with
645 the possible personal benefits achieved such as reduced pollutant exposure. It was found that
646 around 34 % of the participants in the study group have the availability of walking/cycling routes
647 with significantly less pollutant exposure (with a difference $\geq 10 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ of NO_2 concentration) as
648 compared to current routes. Further based on the responses in the feedback questionnaire, it was
649 observed that for those participants where lower polluted alternatives are available, 77 % of such
650 participants started following the suggested alternatives school routes. These findings provide
651 evidence that this intervention can significantly promote school commuting focusing on least
652 pollutant exposed routes. There is a clear potential for such soft interventions to be instigated on a

653 wider scale with a correspondingly larger impact on individual health and wellbeing. As the
654 benefits of reduction in pollutant exposure are considered in conjunction with the well-established
655 health benefits of physical activity, such intervention based initiatives should be attractive to local
656 and national governments. Based on the results of the large scale implementation, this intervention
657 study can be further extended by developing a publicly available smartphone application that helps
658 individuals to identify low pollutant walking/cycling routes which can help deliver health benefits
659 for children and other individuals.

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667 **References**

- 668
- 669 1. Air Quality in Europe (2016). EEA Report, vol 28/2016. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the
670 European Union. doi:10.2800/80982
 - 671 2. Review of evidence on health aspects of air pollution - REVIHAAP (2013). REVIHAAP Project: Technical
672 Report. WHO Regional Office for Europe, Scherfigsvej 8, DK-2100 Copenhagen, Denmark
 - 673 3. Air Pollution and Child Health: Prescribing Clean Air (2018). World Health Organization,
 - 674 4. Salvi S (2007) Health effects of ambient air pollution in children. *Paediatr Respir Rev* 8 (4):275-280.
675 doi:10.1016/j.prrv.2007.08.008
 - 676 5. Prüss-Üstün A, Wolf J, Corvalán C, Bos R, Neira M (2016) Preventing disease through healthy
677 environments: a global assessment of the burden of disease from environment risks. World Health
678 Organization. <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/204585>. Accessed 12th of July 2019
 - 679 6. Dons E, Van Poppel M, Int Panis L, De Prins S, Berghmans P, Koppen G, Matheussen C (2014) Land use
680 regression models as a tool for short, medium and long term exposure to traffic related air pollution. *Sci*
681 *Total Environ* 476-477:378-386. doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2014.01.025
 - 682 7. Boniardi L, Dons E, Campo L, Van Poppel M, Int Panis L, Fustinoni S (2019) Annual, seasonal, and
683 morning rush hour Land Use Regression models for black carbon in a school catchment area of Milan,
684 Italy. *Environ Res* 176:108520. doi:10.1016/j.envres.2019.06.001

685 8. Cunha-Lopes I, Martins V, Faria T, Correia C, Almeida SM (2019) Children's exposure to sized-
686 fractioned particulate matter and black carbon in an urban environment. *Building and Environment*
687 155:187-194. doi:10.1016/j.buildenv.2019.03.045

688 9. Alvarez-Pedrerol M, Rivas I, Lopez-Vicente M, Suades-Gonzalez E, Donaire-Gonzalez D, Cirach M, de
689 Castro M, Esnaola M, Basagana X, Dadvand P, Nieuwenhuijsen M, Sunyer J (2017) Impact of commuting
690 exposure to traffic-related air pollution on cognitive development in children walking to school. *Environ*
691 *Pollut* 231 (Pt 1):837-844. doi:10.1016/j.envpol.2017.08.075

692 10. Buonanno G, Marini S, Morawska L, Fuoco FC (2012) Individual dose and exposure of Italian children
693 to ultrafine particles. *Sci Total Environ* 438:271-277. doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2012.08.074

694 11. Nieuwenhuijsen MJ, Donaire-Gonzalez D, Rivas I, de Castro M, Cirach M, Hoek G, Seto E, Jerrett M,
695 Sunyer J (2015) Variability in and agreement between modeled and personal continuously measured
696 black carbon levels using novel smartphone and sensor technologies. *Environ Sci Technol* 49 (5):2977-
697 2982. doi:10.1021/es505362x

698 12. Rivas I, Donaire-Gonzalez D, Bouso L, Esnaola M, Pandolfi M, de Castro M, Viana M, Alvarez-Pedrerol
699 M, Nieuwenhuijsen M, Alastuey A, Sunyer J, Querol X (2016) Spatiotemporally resolved black carbon
700 concentration, schoolchildren's exposure and dose in Barcelona. *Indoor Air* 26 (3):391-402.
701 doi:10.1111/ina.12214

702 13. Buttazzoni AN, Clark AF, Seabrook JA, Gilliland JA (2019) Promoting active school travel in elementary
703 schools: A regional case study of the school travel planning intervention. *Journal of Transport & Health*
704 12:206-219. doi:10.1016/j.jth.2019.01.007

705 14. Coombes E, Jones A (2016) Gamification of active travel to school: A pilot evaluation of the Beat the
706 Street physical activity intervention. *Health Place* 39:62-69. doi:10.1016/j.healthplace.2016.03.001

707 15. Crawford S, Garrard J (2013) A combined impact-process evaluation of a program promoting active
708 transport to school: understanding the factors that shaped program effectiveness. *J Environ Public*
709 *Health* 2013:816961. doi:10.1155/2013/816961

710 16. Hinckson EA, Garrett N, Duncan S (2011) Active commuting to school in New Zealand children (2004-
711 2008): a quantitative analysis. *Prev Med* 52 (5):332-336. doi:10.1016/j.ypmed.2011.02.010

712 17. Hoelscher D, Ory M, Dowdy D, Miao J, Atteberry H, Nichols D, Evans A, Menendez T, Lee C, Wang S
713 (2016) Effects of Funding Allocation for Safe Routes to School Programs on Active Commuting to School
714 and Related Behavioral, Knowledge, and Psychosocial Outcomes. *Environment and Behavior* 48 (1):210-
715 229. doi:10.1177/0013916515613541

716 18. Johnson R, Frearson M, Hewson P (2016) Can bicycle training for children increase active travel?
717 *Proceedings of the Institution of Civil Engineers - Engineering Sustainability* 169 (2):49-57.
718 doi:10.1680/ensu.14.00067

719 19. Sayers SP, LeMaster JW, Thomas IM, Petroski GF, Ge B (2012) A Walking School Bus program: impact
720 on physical activity in elementary school children in Columbia, Missouri. *Am J Prev Med* 43 (5 Suppl
721 4):S384-389. doi:10.1016/j.amepre.2012.07.009

722 20. Vanwolleghem G, D'Haese S, Dyck DV, Bourdeaudhuij ID, Cardon G (2014) Feasibility and
723 effectiveness of drop-off spots to promote walking to school. *International Journal of Behavioral*
724 *Nutrition and Physical Activity* 11:136. doi:10.1186/s12966-014-0136-6

725 21. Xu F, Ware RS, Leslie E, Tse LA, Wang Z, Li J, Wang Y (2015) Effectiveness of a Randomized Controlled
726 Lifestyle Intervention to Prevent Obesity among Chinese Primary School Students: CLICK-Obesity Study.
727 *PLoS One* 10 (10):e0141421. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0141421

728 22. Molter A, Lindley S (2015) Influence of walking route choice on primary school children's exposure to
729 air pollution--A proof of concept study using simulation. *Sci Total Environ* 530-531:257-262.
730 doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2015.05.118

731 23. Adnan M, Ahmed S (2017) Environmental Effects of Behavioural Actions. iSCAPE - Improving the
732 Smart Control of Air Pollution in Europe. <https://www.iscapeproject.eu/scientific-reports/>. Accessed
733 20th of May 2018

734 24. Osbaldiston R, Schott JP (2011) Environmental Sustainability and Behavioral Science. *Environment*
735 *and Behavior* 44 (2):257-299. doi:10.1177/0013916511402673

736 25. Sayers SP, LeMaster JW, Thomas IM, Petroski GF, Ge B (2012) Bike, walk, and wheel: a way of life in
737 Columbia, Missouri, revisited. *Am J Prev Med* 43 (5 Suppl 4):S379-383.
738 doi:10.1016/j.amepre.2012.07.006

739 26. James B (2002) TravelSmart?large-scale cost-effective mobility management. Experiences from Perth,
740 Western Australia. *Municipal Engineer* 151 (1):39-48. doi:10.1680/muen.2002.151.1.39

741 27. Cairns S, Sloman L, Newson C, Anable J, Kirkbride A, Goodwin P (2004) Smarter Choices – Changing
742 the Way We Travel. Department for Transport, London,

743 28. Brög W, Erl E, Ker I, Ryle J, Wall R (2009) Evaluation of voluntary travel behaviour change:
744 Experiences from three continents. *Transport Policy* 16 (6):281-292. doi:10.1016/j.tranpol.2009.10.003

745 29. Schultz PW (2014) Strategies for Promoting Proenvironmental Behavior. *European Psychologist* 19
746 (2):107-117. doi:10.1027/1016-9040/a000163

747 30. Panis LI, Dons E, De Boever P (2016) Health effects of ambient air pollution and how to limit personal
748 exposure. Paper presented at the Respiratory Equipment and Devices Exhibition Magazine,

749 31. de Nazelle A, Morton BJ, Jerrett M, Crawford-Brown D (2010) Short trips: An opportunity for reducing
750 mobile-source emissions? *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment* 15 (8):451-457.
751 doi:10.1016/j.trd.2010.04.012

752 32. Beckx C, Broekx S, Degraeuwe B, Beusen B, Int Panis L (2013) Limits to active transport substitution of
753 short car trips. *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment* 22:10-13.
754 doi:10.1016/j.trd.2013.03.001

755 33. Fellermann A (2015) Guideline for Promotion of Public Transport. Bund für Umwelt und Naturschutz
756 Deutschland (BUND).

757 34. Kim JJ, Smorodinsky S, Lipsett M, Singer BC, Hodgson AT, Ostro B (2004) Traffic-related air pollution
758 near busy roads: the East Bay Children's Respiratory Health Study. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med* 170 (5):520-
759 526. doi:10.1164/rccm.200403-281OC

760 35. Ragettli MS, Phuleria HC, Tsai MY, Schindler C, de Nazelle A, Ducret-Stich RE, Ineichen A, Perez L,
761 Braun-Fahrlander C, Probst-Hensch N, Kunzli N (2015) The relevance of commuter and work/school
762 exposure in an epidemiological study on traffic-related air pollution. *J Expo Sci Environ Epidemiol* 25
763 (5):474-481. doi:10.1038/jes.2014.83

764 36. The Curieuzeneuzen citizen science project. (2016). <http://www.curieuzeneuzen.eu/en/about/>.
765 Accessed 14th of July 2019

766 37. RIO-IFDM-OSPM model. <http://www.irceline.be/nl/documentatie/modellen/rio-ifdm-ospm>.
767 Accessed 15th of June 2018

768 38. Lefebvre W, Van Poppel M, Maiheu B, Janssen S, Dons E (2013) Evaluation of the RIO-IFDM-street
769 canyon model chain. *Atmospheric Environment* 77:325-337. doi:10.1016/j.atmosenv.2013.05.026

770 39. Boniardi L, Dons E, Campo L, Van Poppel M, Int Panis L, Fustinoni S (2019) Is a Land Use Regression
771 Model Capable of Predicting the Cleanest Route to School? *Environments* 6 (8).
772 doi:10.3390/environments6080090

773 40. Schröder S, Karich P, Zilske M GraphHopper Directions API (1.0.0). <https://docs.graphhopper.com/>.
774 Accessed 20th of March 2019

775 41. D'Haese S, De Meester F, De Bourdeaudhuij I, Deforche B, Cardon G (2011) Criterion distances and
776 environmental correlates of active commuting to school in children. , . *International Journal of*
777 *Behavioral Nutrition and Physical Activity* 8:88. doi:10.1186/1479-5868-8-88

- 778 42. Rui T (2016) Modeling Route Choice Behaviour in Public Transport Network. National University of
779 Singapore,
- 780 43. Ahmed S, Adnan M, Janssens D, Brattich E, Yasar A-u-H, Kumar P, di Sabatino S, Shakshuki EM (2018)
781 Estimating pro-environmental potential for the development of mobility-based informational
782 intervention: a data-driven algorithm. *Personal and Ubiquitous Computing*. doi:10.1007/s00779-018-
783 1187-5
- 784 44. Adnan M, Passani A (2017) Report on Behavioural Interventions. vol D1.3. iSCAPE - Improving the
785 Smart Control of Air Pollution in Europe,
- 786 45. Lorquet A, Borret K, De Somer P, De Wever H, Haerens R, Tan P, Van der Veken K, Vermaut Y (2012)
787 Urban development in Antwerp: Designing Antwerp. Patricia De Somer, Grote Markt 1, 2000 Antwerpen
- 788 46. Tang T, Van Brusselen D, Arrazola de Oñate W, Maiheu B, Vranckx S, Lefebvre W, Janssen S, Nawrot
789 TS, Nemery B, Avonts D (2016) Health Impact Assessment of a Predicted Air Quality Change by Moving
790 Traffic from an Urban Ring Road into a Tunnel. The Case of Antwerp, Belgium. *Plos One* 11 (5).
791 doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0154052
- 792 47. Degraeuwe B, Thunis P, Clappier A, Weiss M, Lefebvre W, Janssen S, Vranckx S (2016) Impact of
793 passenger car NOx emissions and NO2 fractions on urban NO2 pollution – Scenario analysis for the city of
794 Antwerp, Belgium. *Atmospheric Environment* 126:218-224. doi:10.1016/j.atmosenv.2015.11.042
- 795 48. Air Quality Standards. (2017) European Environment Agency.
796 <https://www.eea.europa.eu/themes/air/air-quality-standards>. Accessed 17th of July 2019
- 797 49. Dales R, Wheeler A, Mahmud M, Frescura AM, Smith-Doiron M, Nethery E, Liu L (2008) The influence
798 of living near roadways on spirometry and exhaled nitric oxide in elementary schoolchildren. *Environ*
799 *Health Perspect* 116 (10):1423-1427. doi:10.1289/ehp.10943
- 800 50. Barone-Adesi F, Dent JE, Dajnak D, Beevers S, Anderson HR, Kelly FJ, Cook DG, Whincup PH (2015)
801 Long-Term Exposure to Primary Traffic Pollutants and Lung Function in Children: Cross-Sectional Study
802 and Meta-Analysis. *PLoS One* 10 (11):e0142565. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0142565
- 803 51. Heroux ME, Anderson HR, Atkinson R, Brunekreef B, Cohen A, Forastiere F, Hurley F, Katsouyanni K,
804 Krewski D, Krzyzanowski M, Kunzli N, Mills I, Querol X, Ostro B, Walton H (2015) Quantifying the health
805 impacts of ambient air pollutants: recommendations of a WHO/Europe project. *Int J Public Health* 60
806 (5):619-627. doi:10.1007/s00038-015-0690-y
- 807 52. Bowatte G, Lodge C, Lowe AJ, Erbas B, Perret J, Abramson MJ, Matheson M, Dharmage SC (2015) The
808 influence of childhood traffic-related air pollution exposure on asthma, allergy and sensitization: a
809 systematic review and a meta-analysis of birth cohort studies. *Allergy* 70 (3):245-256.
810 doi:10.1111/all.12561
- 811 53. Bergstra AD, Brunekreef B, Burdorf A (2018) The effect of industry-related air pollution on lung
812 function and respiratory symptoms in school children. *Environ Health* 17 (1):30. doi:10.1186/s12940-
813 018-0373-2
- 814 54. Atkinson RW, Butland BK, Anderson HR, Maynard RL (2018) Long-term Concentrations of Nitrogen
815 Dioxide and Mortality: A Meta-analysis of Cohort Studies. *Epidemiology* 29 (4):460-472.
816 doi:10.1097/EDE.0000000000000847
- 817 55. Hatzopoulou M, Weichenthal S, Barreau G, Goldberg M, Farrell W, Crouse D, Ross N (2013) A web-
818 based route planning tool to reduce cyclists' exposures to traffic pollution: a case study in Montreal,
819 Canada. *Environ Res* 123:58-61. doi:10.1016/j.envres.2013.03.004
- 820 56. Larouche R, Mammen G, Rowe DA, Faulkner G (2018) Effectiveness of active school transport
821 interventions: a systematic review and update. *BMC Public Health* 18 (1):206. doi:10.1186/s12889-017-
822 5005-1
- 823 57. McDonald NC, Steiner RL, Lee C, Rhoulac Smith T, Zhu X, Yang Y (2014) Impact of the Safe Routes to
824 School Program on Walking and Bicycling. *Journal of the American Planning Association* 80 (2):153-167.
825 doi:10.1080/01944363.2014.956654

826 58. EUROSTAT (2018), Official EU statistical data, Retrieved from
827 <https://www.eui.eu/Research/Library/ResearchGuides/Economics/Statistics/DataPortal/EDD>

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